

DEVELOPMENT OF ENGLISH COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE OF ENGINEERING STUDENTS

Kholmurodova E'zoza Xasanovna

“Tashkent Institute of Irrigation and Agricultural
Mechanization Engineers” National Research University

English department, English language teacher

Abstract: The article justifies the importance of learning a foreign language for engineering students. Concepts such as competence, professional competence, communication skills, and professional ability to communicate in a foreign language are explained. The characteristics of foreign language learning for students of universities of technology are also defined. Various practical classes used by foreign language teachers are described, and new pedagogical technologies are introduced that ensure the effective development of foreign language skills of technical students.

Keywords: qualification, communication skills, foreign language communication skills, professionally oriented literature.

The increasing demand for skills among young specialists in the labor market has led to a modernization of domestic professional higher education, which seeks to educate individuals in foreign languages alongside linguistic and intercultural education. communication skills, but also professional communication skills in a foreign language. Accordingly, the foreign language training of future experts must aim to develop their communication skills at the level of professional knowledge. To succeed in professional activities, science, modern society, and international communication, students of the technical university must acquire linguistic and cultural skills that form intercultural communication skills in a foreign language.

The development of English communicative competence among engineering students is crucial for their success in the field, as English is often considered the universal language of communication in the engineering industry. Here are some strategies that can help facilitate the development of English communicative competence among engineering students:

- **Integration of English language skills in engineering curriculum:** Engineering programs can incorporate English language courses or modules that focus on technical writing, presentation skills, and communication in a professional setting. This will help students develop the specific language skills needed for their future careers.

- **Utilization of technology:** Technology can be used to provide interactive and engaging learning experiences for students to practice their English communication skills. Online platforms, virtual simulations, and multimedia tools can be used to enhance language learning and provide real-world context for communication.

- **Hands-on projects and group work:** Engineering students can benefit from collaborative projects that require them to communicate with their peers in English. Group work helps students practice speaking, listening, and presenting in a team setting, which are important skills in the workplace.

- **Language support services:** Universities can offer language support services such as tutoring, workshops, and language labs to help engineering students improve their English proficiency. These resources can provide personalized support to address individual needs and challenges.

- **Industry partnerships:** Collaborations with industry partners can provide engineering students with opportunities to engage in real-world projects that require effective communication in English. Internships, co-op programs, and guest lectures from industry professionals can help students apply their language skills in a professional context.

According to this perspective, a person's proficiency in using/mastering the foreign language in various professional contexts can be defined as professional foreign communication skills. In other words, the communicative competence of a foreign language can be considered an important and important part of the professional competence of a future engineer, because it is the mastery of a foreign language and the ability to communicate that makes a highly qualified expert in the field. , which is urgently needed today as a result of the modernization of home education. Teaching a foreign language in technical universities can be classified as promoting communicative competence in the language and helping students solve professional problems related to the foreign country. This is why it is considered part of the teaching of entrepreneurship at university. business communication process using all necessary information. To develop competence in communication with a professional orientation of a foreign language, it is necessary to ensure the practical orientation of the foreign language teaching, namely, the foreign language course should be closely related to several specialist subjects that students study in special courses.

According to the data presented above, technical university students' foreign language education reflects the modern demands of society and concentrates on producing highly skilled professionals. This is particularly true for them in higher education settings. in professional activities and in professional communication in a foreign language. Based on the analysis of "foreign language" work programs and the work of technical teachers, we conclude that the main goal of modern technical colleges is to teach students a foreign language that enables them to communicate freely. on the professional and business level and to further develop your foreign language skills within the framework of professional activities and vice versa, to acquire a new department and improve your professional skills with the help of a foreign language. Overall, a holistic approach that integrates language learning into the engineering curriculum, utilizes technology for interactive learning experiences,

promotes collaboration through group work, provides language support services, and fosters industry partnerships can contribute to the development of English communicative competence among engineering students.

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